

**Motivated Reasoning and the
Decision-Making of Coup Resisters:
Choosing to Leave or Stay in the
Tanintharyi Region, Southern
Myanmar**

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Published By: Center for Tavoy Studies
18 Nov 2025

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ABSTRACT

After the Myanmar military junta suppressed the nationwide anti-coup movement in February 2021, including in the Tanintharyi region of southern Myanmar, many coup resisters fled abroad due to security and survival concerns, while others chose to remain. This research investigated the psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement. The study examined the role of psychological factors, such as personal beliefs, values, and attitudes, and external factors, including family, community, and socioeconomic conditions, in the coup resisters' decision-making. It also examined how psychological factors interact with external factors to shape individual decisions through the lens of theories of motivated reasoning, decision-making, and cognitive dissonance. This research was based on qualitative analysis using primary data sources collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews with 24 coup resisters. The findings aimed to deepen understanding of social dynamics at play among Tanintharyi coup resisters and the perceived consequences of their choices for the broader resistance movement.

Keywords: Cognitive dissonance, Coup resisters, Decision-making, Motivated reasoning, Peacebuilding

INTRODUCTION

Background

After the Myanmar military coup in February 2021, the anti-coup movement rose nationwide, including in the Tanintharyi Region. In response, the Myanmar military brutally suppressed the movement by detaining, torturing, and extrajudicially killing the coup resisters. This climate of fear and violence forced many to flee abroad, while others chose to stay and resist within the country. A few months after the brutal crackdown, the political crisis turned into an armed conflict and spread across the country. Suppressions by the military junta have continued to intensify, with unlawful acts, including destroying civilian properties, burning villages, and airstrikes over civilian areas.

Four years after the coup, more than 6,000 people have been killed and over 20,000 have been detained (Amnesty International, 2025). In addition, over 100,000 civilian homes have been destroyed. (Data for Myanmar, 2025). The crisis has affected all sectors, including education and health care. School enrollment has dropped, with over 20 % of children out of school in the 2023/2024 academic year. The worsening socioeconomic and security conditions have led to a large-scale forced migration. Approximately 3.5 million people have been internally displaced. 3.7 million have migrated to Thailand by 2023. Many of them face exploitation due to their lack of legal status (UN News, 2025).

All of these crises followed the same pattern and situation in the Tanintharyi region. In 2024 alone, over 600 armed clashes between the Myanmar military and the revolutionary forces, nearly 100 air strikes, and 70 drone attacks were conducted by the military junta in the Tanintharyi region. 50,000 to 70,000 people were internally displaced and returned every month. Due to the fluid nature of displacement, the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) and returnees in the Tanintharyi region changes regularly.

In addition, the introduction of a conscription law by the military junta in February 2024 has further accelerated migration out of the region. Most of Tanintharyi's people have fled to Thailand and Malaysia due to geographic proximity to escape forced recruitment, violence,

and socioeconomic crisis (FE5 Tanintharyi, 2025). All these crises: the armed conflict, forced displacement, political repression, and the worsening socioeconomic conditions have led to an examination of how individuals, particularly coup resisters, make decisions to stay or leave.

Problem Statement

The decision to leave or stay in the country has led to social tension and misunderstanding among coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region, Southern Myanmar. These different choices have also created challenges to the unity and coordination within the anti-coup movement. This research investigated the psychological and external factors that shape the decisions of coup resisters through the frameworks of motivated reasoning, cognitive dissonance, and decision-making theory. A deeper understanding of these influential factors and social dynamics is crucial for better cooperation within the resistance movement, future nation-building, and peacebuilding strategies.

Objectives

- (1) To identify the profiles of coup resisters.
- (2) To explore the psychological factors that influence the decision of coup resisters in Tanintharyi.
- (3) To explore the external factors that influence the decision of coup resisters and how psychological factors (personal beliefs, values, and attitudes) interact with them.
- (4) To examine coup resisters' perceptions of the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance and peacebuilding efforts.

Research Question

- (1) What is the profile of coup resisters?
- (2) What psychological factors influence the decision of coup resisters to join the movement and to leave or stay in Tanintharyi?
- (3) What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) influence the decision of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi, and how do psychological factors interact with them?
- (4) How do coup resisters perceive the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance and peacebuilding efforts?

METHODOLOGY

Scope, Limitation, and Delimitation

This section discusses the boundaries of the paper. The scope of the study is the psychological and social dynamics among coup resisters. It focuses on coup resisters from the Tanintharyi Region only, and was interviewed during March-June 2025. And this research did not investigate the momentum and strategies of the anti-coup movement. It will not discuss the active roles of the armed and non-armed coup resisters. Please see **Figure 1** below.

Figure 1: Scope, Limitations, and Delimitations

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Literature Review

This literature review examines the decision-making processes of coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region of Myanmar by drawing on psychological theories and exploring the roles of personal beliefs, values, and attitudes. These concepts provide a lens to understand how coup resisters rationalize their choices to either remain in the country or flee, particularly under conditions of repression and armed conflict.

Coup Resisters

Coup resisters are the individuals or groups resisting Myanmar's 2021 military coup. They are not only persons who actively joined the armed and non-armed struggle, but also civilians who expressed opposition to the military regime in various forms.

In this research, two terms of coup resisters have been used.

- (1) Domestic coup resisters refer to individuals who remain inside the country and resist.
- (2) Exile coup resisters refer to individuals who leave the country and resist.

Beliefs

Collins Dictionary (2025) defines belief as a feeling of certainty that something exists, is true, or is good. They serve as cognitive anchors in decision-making processes and shape how people interpret events, threats, and opportunities. For coup resisters, beliefs about justice, democracy, freedom, and the armed or non-armed struggle inform their choices.

Personal Values

Personal values refer to the core principles or standards of individuals. The principles are important in deciding what is right or wrong, acceptable or unacceptable in people's lives (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025). These values, such as fairness, courage, family, and royalty, often guide moral judgments and long-term commitments, influencing how individuals weigh the risks and consequences of resisting the military regime.

Attitudes

According to the Cambridge Dictionary (2025), an attitude is a way of thinking or behaving influenced by feelings or opinions. In the context of political resistance, attitudes toward the military, resistance groups, and socioeconomic conditions can significantly influence a person's willingness to engage in armed or non-armed movements and stay in the country or leave.

Motivated Reasoning Theory

This theory, introduced by Ziva Kunda (1990), explains how individuals align their beliefs with their desires, often justifying decisions that reflect their goals. For coup resisters, decisions to stay or leave are influenced by their attachments to political beliefs, personal values, and the climate of fear. Rather than seeking objective truth, people often justify decisions that align with their beliefs, personal values, and goals. For coup resisters, motivated reasoning may be used to rationalize the decision to stay or leave and to choose the way and strategy of their involvement in the movement based on attachment to political beliefs and social belonging.

Cognitive Dissonance Theory

Cognitive dissonance (Leon Festinger, 1957) occurs when individuals are confronted with facts that contradict their beliefs, values, and ideas. They will try to find a way to resolve the contradiction to reduce their discomfort. In political crisis environments, such as post-coup Myanmar, this dissonance can manifest in the internal conflict between the desire to resist authoritarian rule and the need to protect oneself or one's family. Individuals often resolve this dissonance by changing their beliefs or reframing their decisions to maintain a sense of psychological comfort.

Decision-Making Theory

Simon's (1947) decision-making theory (Unacademy, 2025)(Antonius Alijoyo, 2021) explains that decisions involve selecting an option among different options and possibilities. It describes how people can make decisions within certain limits of available information, time, and cognitive capacity. People don't always make perfectly logical decisions. They often choose options that are "good enough" rather than the best possible. In the case of coup resisters, decisions to stay or leave are made under extreme stress, uncertainty, and limited choices.

Together, these theories and concepts offer a valuable framework for understanding how coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region justify their actions in the face of moral dilemmas, political violence, and social pressure. They also help explain the variation in responses among coup resisters and the underlying factors shaping resistance directions.

Research Gap

Many studies have examined revolutionary momentum, various strategies of anti-coup movements: the armed and non-armed movements, the key actors: the State Administrative Council (SAC) of Myanmar, Ethnic Revolutionary Organizations (EROs), People Defense Forces (PDF), Political Organizations and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), the impacts of the conflict, such as social, economic, health, and education collapse, human rights violations, humanitarian, mental health. However, there is a lack of studies focusing on the psychological factors that influence individual decision-making. This gap limits a deeper understanding of the internal and external factors that shape resistance behaviors and affect solidarity within the movement. Please see **Table 1** below.

Table 1: Research Questions and Theories

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RQ1 Profiles	Demographics
RQ2: Psychological Factors	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and Decision-making theories
RQ3: External Factors	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and Decision-making theories
RQ4: Perception of Consequences	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and decision-making theories

Research Methodology

This research was based on qualitative analysis by using primary sources of data, including in-depth semi-structured interviews with coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region. Employing the narratives, this research allows the exploration of internal and external factors, personal narratives, and motivations that shape their decisions. The Index of Item Objectives Concurrence (IOC) for interview questions & the research questions was provided. Please see **Appendix (A)**.

Sampling

A purposive sampling method was used to select coup resisters. The sample size included 24 participants to ensure diversity in age, gender, experiences, and perspectives. They were categorized into three age groups: 25-35 (youths), 36-50 (adults), and 51-65 (senior adults).

Data Collection

There are two sources of data collection. The first is primary sources. The second is secondary sources. Primary sources include open-ended, semi-structured interviews and questionnaires. It was conducted via the Zoom platform and self-reports. The interview questions were translated from English to the Myanmar language. The secondary data sources include research articles, such as "The Case of Motivated Reasoning" by Ziva Kanda (1990), and "The Review of Cognitive Dissonance Theory and its Relevance to Current Social Issues" by Azizul Halim Yahya and Vidi Sukmayadi (2020), as well as media resources (Online Dictionary), which were utilized.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using thematic analysis. Themes include profiles, psychological factors, beliefs, values, attitudes, external factors, and perceptions of interviewees regarding the consequences of their decision to stay or leave.

Conceptual Framework

It is a conceptual framework of the study. Please see **Figure 2** below.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

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Benefits of the study

The study contributes to a better understanding of the psychological and social dynamics within resistance movements in Tanintharyi, Southern Myanmar.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings 1

1. Profiles of Coup Resisters

1.1 Demographics of coup resisters

A total of 24 coup resisters participated in this research. 75% were male and 25% were female. 75% were youth aged between 25 and 35 years old, 17% were adults aged between 36 and 50 years old, and 8% were senior adults aged between 51 and 65 years old. Among the participants, 54% held a university degree, while 46% had not yet completed university education. 79% of coup resisters live abroad, while 21% remain in the country.

79% of resisters are Buddhists, 17% are Atheists, and 4% are Agnostics. 79% had experience in advocacy or activism before the coup, while 21% had not. See **Figures 3 and 4** below.

Figure 3: % of interviewees and their religion

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EXPERIENCE IN ACTIVISM BEFORE THE COUP

Figure 4: % of interviewees and their experience in activism

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If it was classified by gender, 13 male and 6 female interviewees are Buddhist, 4 males are Atheist, and a male is Agnostic. 13 males have experience in activism before the coup, and 4 males didn't have. And 6 females didn't have. See **Tables 3 and 4** below.

Table 2: No. of males and females, and their religion

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Gender	Buddhist	Atheist	Agnostic
Male	13	4	1
Female	6	0	0

Table 3: No. of males and females and their experience in activism

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Gender	Have experience in activism before the coup	No experience in activism before the coup
Male	13	4
Female	6	0

The demographic details of the coup resisters' profile are provided. Please see **Appendix (B)**.

1.2 Life Before the Coup

According to the coup resisters from Tanintharyi, life before the coup was generally filled with peace, freedom, and hope for the future. In particular, the period from 2015 to 2020 was described as a time of relative freedom and the rule of law. People were able to move around freely even at midnight. The economy was functioning reasonably well, and there were opportunities for education and employment. Life was pleasant because people could make their own decisions, and they could speak and discuss openly and freely about whatever mattered to them.

1.3 Impact of the Coup

The military coup has negatively affected the socioeconomic condition and individual mental health.

Economy

Businesses could no longer operate normally. There was high inflation, and the prices of goods skyrocketed. Before the coup, the exchange rate was over 1,300 Kyats per USD, but more than four years later, it rose to over 4,000 Kyats per USD. On the other hand, income levels dropped due to the collapse of business activity and the lack of employment opportunities.

Social Life

Many families were separated and displaced. Because the military targeted not only those directly involved in the resistance but also their family members, many had to relocate for safety reasons. In particular, after a conscription law was announced in February 2024, many young people fled from their hometowns. Family planning and long-term plans were often put on hold.

Among domestic coup resisters, there were three groups:

1. Those who stayed in their hometowns acted as if they were involved in nothing.
2. Those who relocated to other regions or towns within the country.

3. Those who fled to liberated areas and became actively involved in armed resistance in various capacities. See **Figure 5** below.

Figure (5) Groups of domestic coup resisters

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Changes in Community Life

Most schools remain closed, especially in rural areas, and local businesses struggle to operate effectively.

Due to declining economic conditions and limited job opportunities, many people have migrated to neighboring countries, such as Thailand and Malaysia, to work as migrant laborers. Those who had previously returned from Thailand to resettle in their hometowns before the coup have shut down their businesses and gone back to Thailand. Others who were planning to return can no longer do so. The enactment of a conscription law has pushed the remaining youth out of the country, forcing them to flee.

As most youth have fled their hometowns, villages are now primarily populated by elders. Local community activities have weakened because the youth who were the main drivers of community activities have departed. Festivals and traditional ceremonies are no longer held as they once were.

In villages closer to towns or among wealthier families, some children continue their education in private schools. Public hospitals and clinics can no longer function properly, and people live in constant fear of clashes or airstrikes. Freedom of speech has been lost, and in social life, there is growing mistrust among individuals, leading to strained relationships.

The groups with ties to the military gain more privileges and opportunities to conduct business. All these issues affected an individual's psychological well-being.

Psychological Impacts

Due to the collapse of everything and the constant state of anxiety, there have been significant psychological impacts. Because family members are scattered in different places, people experience worry and distress. Living with the constant worry and insecurity also affects family and social relationships. Whenever a family member goes out, those left behind live in anxious anticipation until they return safely.

“After the coup, everyone was put in a cage. To speak frankly, it's like we've all been imprisoned in some way. I can only move around within a small area where I'm currently staying.”

Interviewee No. I007-25, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, 38-year-old male, from Launglone Township, Tanintharyi Region

It is a summary of **Finding 1**. Please see **Table 4** below.

Table 4: Summary of Finding 1

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Research Question no.	Finding
RQ 1.1 Demographic	The majority of the coup resisters are young and stay abroad.
RQ 1.2 Life before the coup(2015-2020)	Life was generally filled with peace, freedom, hope, and the rule of law. The economy was functioning well, and there were opportunities for education and employment under civilian leadership.
RQ 1.3 Impact of the coup	<p>Socioeconomic conditions</p> <p>The economy declined. Local businesses struggle to operate. Most schools remain closed. Many families were separated and displaced. The 2024 conscription law led many youths to flee their hometowns. Local community weakened. Freedom of speech lost, social mistrust increased. The groups with ties to the military gain more privileges and opportunities to conduct business.</p> <p>Psychological conditions</p>

	People live in a state of fear due to repression, clashes, or airstrikes. Constant worry and insecurity negatively affected family and social cohesion.
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Findings 2

2. Psychological factors influencing the decisions of coup resisters

2.1 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Military Junta

Coup resisters in this study perceived the military and its authoritarian rule as brutal and inhumane. They viewed the military as a self-serving institution that prioritizes personal or group interests over national interests. It saw itself as the savior of the nation and ruled through fear while attempting to control every aspect of life. The military is also viewed as religiously extremist.

“Their institution is fundamentally wrong. We must deconstruct it. Their ideology is clear: this country must be Buddhist and the rulers must be Burmese.”

Interviewee No. I002-25, Exile coup resister, Agnostic, Male, 34 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

2.2 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Resistance Movement

Although there was no disagreement among participants regarding the value of resistance, they expressed concern when individuals or organizations from both armed and non-armed movements engage in the following:

1. Becoming authoritarian while fighting against authoritarianism.
2. Suppressing fellow resistance members and violating human rights.
3. Exploiting the resistance for personal gain in terms of money or power.
4. A loss of humanity and empathy.
5. Failure to achieve unity among resistance actors, both armed and non-armed movements.
6. Labeling those with differing views as enemies or siding with the military.

“There are ideological differences in politics among the coup-resister groups. I’ve researched coup resisters. Sometimes, they even show authoritarian behavior. When I realized that, I began to question the idea that resisting authoritarianism always means you are not authoritarian yourself.”

Interviewee No. I019-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Female, 22 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

Some coup resisters also expressed doubt due to the lack of visible progress and the negative consequences of armed and non-armed struggle, including the political formation for the future of Tanintharyi. These factors led them to become skeptical of resistance and the idea of defeating military rule through armed and non-armed resistance.

2.3 Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement

Coup resisters in this study reported that the following psychological factors drove their participation in resisting authoritarianism:

1. A desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, and justice.
2. A sense of standing on the side of truth.
3. A feeling of moral obligation, especially as they saw people younger than themselves taking up arms.
4. A refusal to return to the military dictatorship period: it is before 2010, when the military junta allowed the wealthy and powerful to do things without justice.
5. A desire to prevent future generations from experiencing the underdevelopment caused by military rule. See **Figure 6** below.

Figure (6): Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement
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2.4 Motivations behind the decision to stay or leave

Exile coup resisters said personal values or beliefs did not primarily influence their decision. The external factors are most influential in their departure.

On the other hand, domestic coup resisters expressed a deep desire to be actively involved in the revolution and to avoid being separated from the ground and their families.

“If I leave the country, it will feel like I’ve stepped away from the armed revolution. If we all left, then who would fight this armed revolution and make it successful? I believe the revolution exists on the ground. So I’ve decided to stay in this land, with these people, and join the resistance to free them.”

Interviewee No. I023-25, Domestic coup resister, Atheist, Male, 23 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of Finding 2. Please see **Table 5** below.

Table 5: Summary of Finding 2

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Research question no.	Finding
<p>2.1 Coup resisters’ perceptions toward the Military Junta</p>	<p>Brutal, inhumane, and self-serving institution. Religious extremists,</p>
<p>2.2 Coup resisters’ perceptions toward the Resistance Movement</p>	<p>No disagreement regarding the value of the resistance. But concerns on actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Becoming authoritarian - Suppressing fellow resistance members - Violating human rights - Exploiting the resistance for personal gains - Lack of unity and visible progress - No progress in the political formation for the future of Tanintharyi
<p>2.3 Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, and justice - Standing on the side of truth - Moral obligation - Commitment to refuse the underdevelopment caused by military rule.

2.4 Motivations behind the decision to stay or leave	<p>Domestic Coup Resisters</p> <p>Political belief, values, and a deep desire to be actively involved in the revolution and to avoid being separated from the ground and their families.</p> <p>Exile Coup Resisters</p> <p>The external factors are most influential in their departure to go abroad.</p>
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Findings 3

3.1 External factors influenced the decision to stay or leave Tanintharyi

Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed. Among exile coup resisters, security was found to be the most influential factor in their decision, followed by personal experience as the second most significant, and friends as the third. Family influence came fourth, while community and media/social media had the least influence. See the table (6) below.

Table 6: Influential factors on exile coup resisters leaving the country
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Influential Factor	Security	Family	Friend	Community	Media/ Social Media	Personal Experience
Numbers resister	18	9	13	7	7	15

In contrast, domestic coup resisters also faced pressure from security risks and other forms of stress. However, they actively sought ways to remain and continue their involvement. Their decision to stay was primarily driven by their values on family, family situation, and the nature of their work to be physically present and involved in the movement on the ground. See the table (7) below.

Table 7: Influential factors on domestic coup resisters remaining in the country
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Influential Factor	Security	Family	Friend	Community	Media/ Social Media	Personal Experience
Number of resisters	0	3	0	0	0	0

“The most important thing is that the work I do requires me to see and hear things firsthand. I believe that brings me closer to the truth. If I live abroad, how will I cover the news? Would I be able to work freely?”

Interviewee No. I024-25, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 37 years old, Launglone, Tanintharyi

3.2

How do personal beliefs, values, and attitudes interact with the external factors

Both exile and domestic coup resisters demonstrated an awareness of the external and internal factors influencing their decisions, as reflected in their responses.

However, the interactions between psychological factors (such as personal beliefs, values, and attitudes) and the external factors (such as security, family, personal experiences, friends, etc.) were not clearly articulated by most coup resisters. And some were not even consciously aware of this interaction between psychological factors and external factors in their decision-making process.

"Other than wanting to leave, I didn't really think deeply about anything else. I didn't have any special or serious thoughts."

Interviewee No.I003-25, Exile coup resister, Atheist, Male, 24 years old, Myeik, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of Finding 3. Please see **Table 8** below.

Table 8: Summary of Finding 3

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Research question no.	Findings
<p>3.1</p> <p>External factors influenced the decision to stay or leave Tanintharyi</p>	<p>Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed.</p> <p>Exile coup resisters</p> <p>Security, Personal experience, Friends, Community, Media/Social Media.</p>

	<p>Domestic coup resisters</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters also faced pressure from security risks and other forms of stress from all directions. However, they decided to remain for their deep value on family life and participating in the movement on the ground physically.</p>
<p>3.2</p> <p>How do your personal beliefs, values, and attitudes interact with the external factors</p>	<p>The interactions between psychological factors and the external factors were not clearly articulated by most coup resisters. And some were not even consciously aware of it.</p>

Findings 4

4. The Perception of coup resisters on the consequences of their decisions for future peacebuilding

4.1 Social and psychological dynamics among the coup resisters

Divisions have existed between domestic and exile resisters. These groups often differ in their perspectives during discussions about resistance-related works. The coup resisters pointed out the following triggers:

“On ground” Vs. “On air”

Domestic resisters emphasized that real resistance must be grounded in the lived experiences of the people. They believed that being physically with the people allows for a genuine understanding of the pain and the desire for peace. They argued that some emotional truths cannot be grasped from afar and must be felt with the heart. Domestic resisters often criticized those overseas, believing they lack understanding of on-the-ground realities. Some resisters noted that exile coup resisters sometimes express overly bold opinions.

In contrast, Many exile coup resisters believe they could better support the resistance once in a safer location. Some believe their skills are better utilized from abroad, including in logistic support, humanitarian aid, fundraising, and digital activism. Some domestic resisters also agreed on this view.

Many of the coup resisters believe that how they participate in the resistance is more important than where they are located. For those abroad, maintaining a connection with the struggle and not forgetting the ground realities is essential.

One critique was that people holding key responsibilities in the resistance should remain on the ground, instead of residing abroad. There is concern that if many key resisters leave, the movement inside the country will weaken.

“The real resistance fighters are on the ground. If you're not physically living with those fighting, you can't fully understand their feelings about peace. Some things can't be heard with the ears. You must listen with the heart. To do that, you need to be close, heart to heart.”

Interviewee No.I007, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 38 years old, Launglone, Tanintharyi

“Domestic life” Vs. “Exile life”

And domestic coup resisters often perceived that people living overseas have more comfortable lives. Those abroad feel misunderstood regarding their difficulties abroad, such as not having proper work, legal status, and security. Social media further amplifies this divide. Pictures posted by those exiles showing outings and comfortable lifestyles reinforce domestic perceptions that these individuals are detached from the daily struggles.

There were also perceptions that some resisters have left for foreign countries due to dreams of living in third countries with refugee status.

Information and Communications

Differences in access to information, lived experiences, and day-to-day realities often lead to disagreements. A key concern is the lack of open and mutual communication. There is a general perception that information sharing and communication between domestic and exile resisters is insufficient to improve mutual understanding.

This group-based mindset (Us Vs Them mindset) can also influence political opinions.

“This kind of division and blame-shifting only delays the revolution and increases the suffering. Our usual approach is weak on unity toward a solution. Pointing fingers at each other won't change anything. What we should ask is, ‘How can each person contribute from where they are?’ ”

Interviewee No. I002-25, Exile coup resister, Male, Agnostic, 34 years old, Dawei-Tanintharyi

4.2 Impact on future peacebuilding efforts

The majority of participants believed that most people who leave abroad will get more chances to gain open perspectives, diverse work experience, and further educational experiences. These experiences are seen as potentially beneficial for the country's future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.

“Ideally, the split between domestic and overseas efforts should be strategic. For example, some should be sent to study. But what we're seeing now isn't systematic. People are just doing what they can, based on their circumstances.”

Interviewee No. I021-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 45 years old, Dawei-Taninthari

However, if the divide is viewed solely through the lens of domestic ("On-Ground") versus exiles ("On-Air"), it can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult.

After the revolution, different views were likely to emerge regarding those who stayed versus those who left. Some may accept the reasons people left, while others may hold resentments, perceiving that those abroad only returned after the struggle ended.

“There will be two classes. One will be the 'elite coup resister,' and the other will be the 'on-ground coup resister. Imagine the 15th anniversary of the revolution. A political elite who lived in Chiang Mai will deliver a keynote about how they resisted, while someone who spent the entire time as an on-ground coup resister will sit quietly in the corner. Our society will always have these two social classes.”

Interviewee No. I001-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 32 years old, Yaybhyu, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of finding 2. Please see **Table 8** below.

Table 8: Summary of Finding 4

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Research question no.	Finding
<p>4.1</p> <p>Social and psychological dynamics among the coup resisters</p>	<p>Divisions have existed between domestic and exile coup resisters.</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters' views</p> <p>Exile coup resisters left for more comfortable lives. They lack understanding of on-the-ground realities and sometimes express overly bold opinions.</p> <p>Most domestic resisters believe that real resistance must be grounded.</p> <p>Exile coup resisters' views</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters misunderstand the difficulties of exile and migrant life.</p> <p>Many exile coup resisters believe they can better support the resistance once in a safer location, according to their skills.</p> <p>Most common view</p> <p>How they participate in the resistance is more important than where they are located. Maintaining a connection with the struggle and not forgetting the ground realities is essential.</p> <p>Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Differences in access to information and knowing realities. (2) Lack of open and mutual communication. (3) Social media: Pictures posted by those exiles show outings and comfortable lifestyles.
<p>4.2</p> <p>Impact on future peacebuilding efforts</p>	<p>Division can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult. Many resisters hope that exile experiences, such as work and education, are seen as potentially beneficial for the country's future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.</p>

SUMMARY

The following is a summary of the influencing factors and decision-making processes of coup resisters, based on the different decisions they made.

Finding 1 for RQ1:

The majority of the coup resisters are young and stay abroad. Life was generally filled with peace, freedom, hope, and the rule of law. All sectors were negatively affected by the military coup and declined.

Finding 2 for RQ2:

Coup resisters perceived the military as inhumane, religious extremists, and a self-serving institution. There is no disagreement among coup resisters regarding the value of the resistance. However, they are concerned when some individuals or groups become authoritarian and act similarly to a junta.

Coup resisters were motivated by the desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, justice, and moral obligation to involve the movement.

Personal values or beliefs did not primarily influence the decisions of exile coup resisters, while external factors were the most influential to flee. In contrast, domestic coup resisters strongly stand on their family values and belief in the revolution.

Finding 3 for RQ3:

Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed. Among exile coup resister, security was the most influential factor in their decision. Domestic coup resisters also faced similar pressure. However, they decided to remain for their deep value in family life and their physical participation in the movement.

Finding 4 for RQ4:

Division can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult for the country's future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.

DISCUSSION

As previously discussed, the psychological and external factors influenced the resisters differently, with domestic actors often driven by values and commitment, and exiles responding primarily to external pressures such as safety and opportunity.

However, this section will discuss the role of cognitive capacity and creating personal narratives.

Cognitive Capacity

Many of them stated that they were not particularly aware of these internal psychological influences and their interaction with external factors. Decision-Making Theory (Simon, 1947), particularly its emphasis on bounded rationality, reflects that limited time, information, and cognitive capacities can affect decision-making.

These findings gave rise to the following questions:

(1) Cognitive Capacity and Climate of Fear

What is the relation between cognitive capacity and climate of fear?

Did a lack of awareness of psychological factors and their interactions occur because of limited cognitive capacity, or the climate of fear led to extreme stress and uncertainty, or both? Can the climate of fear also impact cognitive capacity positively?

(2) Cognitive Capacity and Sense of Urgency

Due to security concerns, many of the resisters leave the country with a sense of urgency, more or less. So, what is the role of a sense of urgency in cognitive capacity? Can a sense of emergency also impact cognitive capacity positively?

Holding beliefs and creating personal narratives

Differences in perceptions and attitudes between those resisting from within the country and those from abroad reflect what is described in Motivated Reasoning (Ziva Kunda, 1990) and Cognitive Dissonance Theory (Leon Festinger, 1957). Individuals hold onto positions that align with their self-interest or established beliefs.

Notably, while domestic resisters claim that they understand their counterparts abroad, they tend to hold the belief that resistance is more effective on the ground. Similarly, exile resisters emphasize that the way they participate is more important than where they participate from.

Implications for resistance and peacebuilding

Understanding the psychological dynamics behind individuals' decisions, as well as the social dynamics developing or potentially emerging among coup resisters, is crucial for both individual actors and resistance groups. Only deep insight and strategic engagement can strengthen the current resistance efforts and help future peacebuilding processes proceed with fewer obstacles.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the psychological and external social factors that influenced the coup resisters' decision to join the anti-coup movement and either stay in the country or flee abroad. It focused on the Tanintharyi region in Southern Myanmar. The findings indicated that both domestic and exile coup resisters are strongly motivated to oppose the military junta and to restore democracy, freedom, and justice. A sense of moral obligation also played a significant role in the decision-making process. However, the motivations and decision outcomes differed based on social status, community context, perceived security risks, and individual values and beliefs. Domestic coup resisters were primarily driven by internal psychological factors, including personal beliefs, values, and a sense of moral obligation, whereas exile coup resisters were influenced by external factors, such as concerns for their own and their families' safety, experiences of repression, and access to opportunities. These differences reflected deeper psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement, which need to be recognized and addressed to strengthen unity and collaboration in the long term of the anti-coup movement and to guide future peacebuilding strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- (1) The coup resisters should recognize that individuals have different rationalities and the right to make personal choices regarding how they participate in the movement.
- (2) The individuals and organizations should strengthen the recognition of mutual roles and interdependence between domestic and exile coup resisters.
- (3) Alternative communication channels, instead of online platforms, should be explored for better communication and mutual respect among resisters.
- (4) Movement leaders should develop strategic approaches to determine whether to be domestic or exile coup resisters for the long-term movement and future peacebuilding and nation-building efforts.
- (5) Psychological education on rationality, decision-making, and cognitive awareness should be integrated into the movement.

APPENDIX

Appendix A: Index of Item Objectives Concurrence (IOC)

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Number	Research Question	Semi-Structured Interview Questions
RQ 1	What is the profile of coup resisters?	<p>RQ 1.1 Can you tell me about your background (e.g., Age, Gender, Religion, Township, Current residence, education, profession, experience in activism)?</p> <p>RQ 1.2 What was your life like before the coup?</p> <p>RQ 1.3 How has the coup affected your life, family, friends, and community?</p>
RQ 2	What psychological factors influence the decision of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi?	<p>RQ 2.1 How would you describe your perception toward the Military Junta?</p> <p>RQ 2.2 How would you describe your perception toward the resistance movement?</p> <p>RQ 2.3 What do your psychological factors (Attitudes, Personal Values, Beliefs, etc) motivate you to resist the coup by the military junta?</p> <p>RQ 2.4 What do your psychological factors (Attitudes, Personal Values, Beliefs, etc) motivate you to leave or stay in the country after the coup?</p>
RQ 3	What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) influence the decision	<p>RQ 3.1 What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) do influence your decision-</p>

	of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi, and how psychological factors interact with them?	making process to stay or leave the Tanintharyi, and how? RQ 3.2 How do your personal beliefs, values, and attitude interact with the external factors in the decision-making process to stay or leave?
RQ 4	How do anti-coup defenders perceive the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance?	RQ 4.1 Have you noticed any psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement regarding staying or leaving the Tanintharyi? RQ 4.2 How do you perceive your decision will impact the resistance movement and future peacebuilding efforts in Myanmar?

Appendix B: The List of Interviewees' Profiles

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No.	Gender	Age	Title	University Education	Home Town	Current Place	Religion
I001-25	Male	32	Digital Officer	Graduated	Yaybhyu, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I002-25	Male	34	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Agnostic
I003-25	Male	24	Journalist	3 rd Year-Engineering	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Atheist
I004-25	Male	41	Chief Reporter	High School	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Ranaung, Thailand	Buddhist
I005-25	Male	26	Journalist	Graduated	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Atheist
I006-25	Female	30	Accountant	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I007-25	Male	38	Journalist	3 rd Year-History	LaungLone, Tanintharyi	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Buddhist
I008-25	Male	58	Professor	Post-Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Buddhist
I009-26	Male	64	Political Activist	2 nd Year-Philosophy	Kyunt Su, Tanintharyi	Hua Hin, Thailand	Buddhist
I010-25	Female	31	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I011-25	Male	24	Graphic Designer	2 nd year-Law	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Yangon, Myanmar	Buddhist
I012-25	Male	26	Barista	Graduated	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I013-25	Male	25	Social Worker	5 th Year-Engineering	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I014-25	Male	35	General Worker	High School	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Surattharni, Thailand	Buddhist
I015-25	Female	25	Graphic Designer	4 th Year-Engineering	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist

I016-25	Female	26	Student	Post-Graduated	Tayetchaung, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I017-25	Male	29	Finance Officer	Graduated	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I018-25	Male	35	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I019-25	Female	22	Presenter	1 st Year-Engineering	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I020-25	Female	25	Journalist	Graduated	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I021-25	Male	45	Digital Editor	Post-Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Maesot, Thailand	Buddhist
I022-25	Male	28	Teacher	4 th Year-Myanmar , Dip-Ed	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Myeik, Thailand	Atheist
I023-25	Male	32	Rebel	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Atheist
I024-25	Male	37	Journalist	High School	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Buddhist

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